

AspirE

Asian prospects
in (re)migration
to/within the EU

Third report on the impact of dissemination strategies

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ABBREVIATIONS

CEPS = Centre for European Policy Studies

CD&E = Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

DPO = Data Protection Officer

EC = European Commission

ECRs = Early Career Researchers

EP = European Parliament

EU = European Union

EUHK = The Education University of Hong Kong

GA = Grant Agreement

GDPR = General Data Protection Regulation

GUF = Goethe University Frankfurt

HE = Horizon Europe

Iscte = University Institute of Lisbon

IS-VASS = Institute of Sociology-Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences

MAU = Mahidol University

MS = Member States

MU = Masaryk University

NGO = Non-governmental organisations

ORE = Open Research Europe

PI = Principal Investigator

REA = Research Executive Agency

SMC = Scalabrini Migration Center

TAU = Tampere University

ULB = Université libre de Bruxelles

UMIL = University of Milan

VAPEC = Vietnam Asia-Pacific Economic Center

WP = Work Package

WUT = Waseda University

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document constitutes the third and final report on the impact of AspirE's dissemination strategies. AspirE is an EU-funded project investigating the decision-making processes of aspiring (re)migrants across 11 countries in Asia and Europe, generating empirical and comparative insights of relevance to both academic research and policy practice. In the context of EU-funded research, dissemination is not only a requirement but a key mechanism to maximise the societal and scientific value of project outputs, ensuring that knowledge reaches the audiences who can use, apply, or further develop it.

Built on the foundations of the previous two reports, this document provides a comprehensive overview of the effectiveness of AspirE's communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities in reaching both academic and non-academic audiences. It highlights the project's main dissemination strategies, including open-access publications and presentations, and evaluates the impact of the principal communication channels. Covering the entire duration of the project from its beginning in January 2023 to its conclusion in February 2026, this report aims to synthesise AspirE's dissemination and exploitation efforts, provide insights into how these strategies contributed to the visibility of the project's outputs, and share key performance indicators.

Keywords

Report, communication, dissemination, exploitation, AspirE

INTRODUCTION

AspirE is a project funded by the European Research Executive Agency (REA) that investigates the decision-making processes of aspiring (re)migrants across 11 countries in Asia and Europe. The project is built on a series of work packages (WPs), including empirical ones encompassing a variety of data collection: policy content analysis and interviews with migration experts (WP2), interviews with aspiring (re)migrants and mapping of their social network (WP3), video diaries of aspiring (re)migrants and two-step focus group discussion with migration experts (WP4). Every year, as part of its impact WP, AspirE produces a report assessing the impact of its dissemination strategies on the visibility, reach, and circulation of the project's activities and research findings. Considering this report covers the entire lifespan of the project (January 2023 to February 2026), the exploitation of results will also be presented.

Dissemination and exploitation constitute core components of the project's Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CD&E) Plan (see Figure 1 below) and are designed to enhance both the impact of AspirE's work. These strategies target a range of audiences: the international academic community engaged in migration research across disciplines, including sociology, anthropology, law, geography, and psychology; policymakers operating at the European Union (EU) and Member State (MS) levels; Asian civil society organisations addressing migration-related issues; aspiring (re)migrants; and the wider public.

Figure 1. AspirE's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

As AspirE reaches the final stage of its implementation, data collection related to the empirical work packages has been completed (early 2025), and the project has fully transitioned into analysis, dissemination, and exploitation activities. This document provides a non-exhaustive overview of the activities carried out over the course of the project at both the coordinating and partner levels. It also evaluates the effectiveness of the various communication tools employed to enhance the visibility and uptake of AspirE's activities and findings, including the project website, social media accounts, and newsletters.

While earlier reports focused on planned activities and their progressive implementation, this final report takes a retrospective perspective and assesses dissemination efforts across the project's full lifetime. Any deviations from the initial CD&E Plan are noted where relevant. Overall, implementation has remained closely aligned with the original strategy, with adjustments reflecting emerging opportunities and the evolving nature of the project.

1. DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES AND EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

Within EU-funded projects, [dissemination refers to making research processes and results public, while exploitation focuses on making a concrete use of results](#). Throughout its implementation, AspirE set up a diversified dissemination strategy combining open-access publication, academic and non-academic presentations, and targeted engagement initiatives. These include in-house productions such as research reports, Policy Briefs, as well as project-led activities such as webinars and trainings. In addition, dissemination has extended beyond traditional formats (i.e., exhibitions, documentary films, a comic book).

To ensure systematic monitoring of AspirE’s activities, an internal tracking mechanism was established to collect information on team members’ publications and related dissemination and exploitation activities. Through a dedicated Google form, partners could share details which would be shared through AspirE’s communication channels (website, social media accounts, and its bimonthly Newsletter). This approach ensured consistent outreach across platforms. The present section provides an overview of those activities along with available key performance indicators.

1.1. Open-access publications

Open-access publishing is a central pillar of AspirE’s dissemination strategy, ensuring that findings remain freely accessible to academic, policy, and civil society audiences. Publications produced during 2024 were detailed and assessed in the [second report on the impact of dissemination activities](#). The present report provides a summary of additional academic publications released in the concluding phase of the project.

- [Migration Intermediation and Ethical Boundary Work: the Case of Italy’s Legal-Administrative Field](#) – Published in the Journal of International Migration and Integration, this article examines how intermediaries in Italy’s migration system navigate ethical dilemmas while assisting with visas and residence permits. Based on 27 interviews, it identifies diverse actors facing a series of challenges. Using the concept of ethical boundary work, the authors show how intermediaries both help and limit migrants’ legal access, sometimes bending rules but also reproducing inequalities. The study highlights tensions between profit and solidarity, empowerment and exploitation, and offers policy recommendations for transparency, regulation, and fair access to legal support.
- [‘Just look at those shabby trains in Lisbon’: post-arrival disappointment amongst Chinese migrants in Portugal](#) – This article was published in the Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies and explores the experiences of affluent Chinese migrants in Portugal, highlighting a gap between their high pre-migration expectations and post-arrival realities. Based on 27 interviews with migrants arriving via Golden Visas, D7 visas, work, and study programs, it shows that frustrations with public services, infrastructure, and cultural life often manifest as boredom. Despite these challenges, the research finds that such discontent can prompt proactive strategies, including adjusting goals, revising financial plans, or considering onward migration to better match expectations with everyday life.
- [Pretending to be Domestic Workers to be ‘Legal’. Uneven Performances of Deservingness Within Italy’s Labour Migration Regime](#) – Published in the Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies, this article examines how Italy’s labour immigration system pushes migrants to present themselves as “deserving” domestic workers in order to obtain residence permits. Based on fieldwork and interviews, it shows that while some migrants successfully navigate amnesties and quota systems by performing this

category, many others face fraud, deception, and legal precarity. The study highlights the arbitrariness of legalization processes and the unequal outcomes produced by state-imposed categories.

- **(Im)mobility Aspirations and Imagined Pathways of Young Migrant Descendants in Portugal** – This contribution is a chapter of the book entitled *Families and Migration: Examining the Human Meaning of Migration*. It presents the imagination and aspirations based on 79 in-depth interviews with young people of Chinese, Brazilian, and Ukrainian descent living in Portugal. This book chapter provides insights on the influence of migratory background on future-making in terms of (im)mobility aspirations.
- **A Confluence of Interests in Filipino Seafarers' Employment on EU- Flagged Ships: The European Commission as Regulatory Intermediary in Philippine Compliance to the STCW Convention** – This article was published in the *International Migration* journal, and it examines how the European Commission, via the European Maritime Safety Agency, monitored Philippine compliance the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification, and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW) from 2006 onward. Using interviews and document analysis, it highlights how alignment of interests between the regulator, intermediary, and target enabled major reforms in the Philippines' maritime administration, ensuring continued EU recognition of Filipino seafarers' certificates and their employment on EU-flagged ships.
- **Geoarbitrage at the Meso Level: How Intermediaries Shape Chinese Migration to Portugal** – Published in the *International Migration* journal, this paper studies geoarbitrage in the context of Chinese migrants seeking Portugal's Golden Visa, focusing on the role of intermediaries. Based on interviews, policy analysis, and consultant materials, it shows how meso-level actors shape Portugal's appeal by mediating between migrants' resources and legal frameworks. The study extends the concept of geoarbitrage beyond individual decision-making, highlighting intermediaries as "geoarbiters" and discussing implications for migration policy and destination attractiveness.

With regard to academic publications, several joint publications remain ongoing and extend beyond the duration of the project. More specifically, collaborative work is being consolidated through a special issue bringing together contributions from work packages 2, 3, and 4, as well as an edited volume integrating key findings across these same work packages. For instance, the last 2 publications listed above are part of AspirE's forthcoming collection of empirical papers in the *International Migration* journal. These collective outputs aim to join efforts to synthesise AspirE's empirical and conceptual contributions and ensure scholarly impact. It must be highlighted that additional team-level publications are on the pipeline.

In parallel to peer-reviewed academic outputs, AspirE has produced a series of in-house publications aimed at broadening accessibility and facilitating practical uptake among both academic and non-academic audiences. These outputs are also fully open access. An overview of these publications is provided below.

- **News articles from The Isaan Record**: While AspirE is mainly composed of academic partners, The Isaan Record stands out as an independent media outlet focusing on social, political, and environmental issues in the Isaan region (northeast of Thailand). Prior to joining AspirE, they had not yet covered the berry-picking activity in northern Europe. Through a series of news contributions and features (in [Thai](#) and [English](#)), project members shared insights emerging from AspirE's research, helping to communicate the

realities on the ground of Thai berry pickers to a broader readership and to stimulate discussion on this specific migration-related dynamic. Their news articles generate active engagement with their audience, with one investigative feature going [viral on Facebook](#), reaching 6,5k reactions and shared about 1,6k times.

- **Policy Briefs** : Policy Briefs constitute an important component of AspirE’s dissemination towards policymakers and stakeholders. Drawing on the project’s mixed qualitative methodology, six Policy Briefs were produced addressing three core objectives: assessing how mobility policies account for aspiring migrants’ behaviour, identifying micro- and meso-level drivers of migration aspirations, and examining the temporal dynamics of (non-)mobility decision-making. Altogether, the Policy Briefs were downloaded 540 times at the time of writing. Project partners were encouraged to produce local-level Briefs to reach regional audiences. This can be illustrated with the policy brief on the [governance of Thai wild berry pickers in Finland](#) produced by Mahidol University and Mahidol Migration Center as well as a [Policy Brief based on findings from the Philippines](#), drafted by the Scalabrini Migration Center.
- **Training Curriculum** : This resource was developed to support researchers working with qualitative methods. Based on three training sessions organised within the project, it provides practical guidance on research [ethics](#), [qualitative data analysis workflows](#) (including tools such as NVivo, ATLAS.ti, and Network Canvas), and [open data principles](#). The curriculum aims to equip researchers, students, and practitioners with the skills needed to conduct, manage, and share qualitative research responsibly and transparently. The training curriculum was downloaded 5 times.
- **AspirE Toolbox** : Sub-titled “Practical resources for those working with or for (aspiring) re/migrants” and downloaded 16 times, the AspirE Toolbox compiles the outputs developed throughout the project, why they matter, and how to use them. The target audience is individuals working on and/or interested in migration-related matters
- **Informative reports**: Aside from country and EU-level reports, all in all downloaded 955 times, and presented in the second report on the impact of dissemination strategies, AspirE produced other kinds of reports. Three reports on the impact of dissemination strategies, including this one, a [report on the dissemination of Policy Briefs](#), and an [advocacy report](#). While the first two dissemination strategies reports have been downloaded 67 times, no statistics are yet available for the other reports since they have been recently published on the project website.
- **Comic book** : AspirE also mobilised a more creative form of communication through the development of a comic book based on selected migration stories collected during the project. Produced in collaboration with Taiwanese illustrator and linguist Jimmeh Aitch, the publication translates research insights into illustrated narratives, offering an accessible way share insights of the lived experiences behind migration trajectories to audiences beyond academia.

1.2 Presentations

Presentations constitute a key component of AspirE’s dissemination activities, providing opportunities to share findings, exchange with stakeholders, and engage diverse audiences. As outlined in Figure 1, these activities take multiple forms, including webinars, policy-oriented events, online and onsite exhibitions, as well as participation in and organisation of academic conferences.

WEBINARS

AspirE organised three webinars to disseminate key insights emerging from its empirical WPs. Each event was supported by a dedicated promotional flyer and programme to maximise visibility and participation among academic, policy, and practitioner audiences.

The first webinar, entitled “*Aspiring (re-)migrants’ behaviour in mobility policies*”, took place on 29-30 January 2024 and drew on findings from WP2 on the socio-legal context of migration decision-making. The event was organised by the University of Milan (UMIL, WP2 coordinator) with the support of the Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB) and gathered 46 participants on the first day and 54 on the second. The second webinar, “*Micro- and meso-level drivers of (re)migration*”, focused on results from WP3, which examines the individual and relational factors shaping migration aspirations and decisions. Organised by ULB on 30 September 2024, the event recorded 72 registered participants. The third webinar, “*Temporality of (re)migration decisions*”, took place on 29-30 April 2025 and presented research conducted within WP4 on the temporal dimension of migration decision-making. The webinar was organised by the University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte, WP4 coordinator) with the support of ULB and counted 73 registered participants, with 34 participants attending on the first day and 37 on the second day.

CONFERENCES

AspirE team members are encouraged and expected to present findings in international conferences, which is one of the many milestones associated with the project. Below is a non-exhaustive list of conferences and other similar public events (e.g., workshops, seminars, webinars) in which AspirE team members participated to share their research findings. This covers the period of January 2025 until December 2026, and it includes public events organised by AspirE at the coordinator level and the partner level (blue background).

Date	Event name & organiser(s)	Participant(s)	Location
27/02 – 02/03/2025	<i>Social Network Mapping Workshop</i> by the Education University of Hong Kong team (EUHK)	Academics, students	Hong Kong (hybrid)
07/03/2025	<i>(Temporary) Labour Migration and Agriculture in the EU: Time, Borders, and Vulnerabilities</i> by the European Birds of Passage project	Academics and a representative of the TAU team	Strasbourg, France
27/03/2025	<i>Annual Meeting of the American Association of Geographers (AAG)</i> by the AAG	Representative of the TAU team	Detroit, USA (hybrid)
22/05/2025	<i>Innovative Qualitative Methods in Migration Research</i> by the sister project DYNAMIG	AspirE’s Principal Investigator and WP4 co-coordinator	London (hybrid)
18/03/2025	<i>Migration Conversations with Pietro Genovese</i> by the Scalabrini Migration Center team (SMC)	Academics and students interested in migration research	Quezon City, the Philippines
25/04/2025	<i>Charting the Stars: Where Purpose Meets Profession</i> by the	Students, career and advocacy organisation	Manila, the Philippines

	Ateneo Association of European Studies Students	representatives, SMC team	
28/05/2025	<i>Revisiting and Prospecting Philippines-to-Europe Migration: New Trends and Policy Implications</i> by the SMC team	Representatives from government agencies, recruitment agencies, embassies, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) academics, and students	Quezon City, the Philippines
01/07/2025	<i>7th edition of the Labour Law Research Network (LLRN)</i> by the LLRN and the Chulalongkorn University	Academics and a representative of the TAU team	Bangkok, Thailand
01 - 04/07/2025	<i>22nd IMISCOE Annual Conference: decentering migration studies</i> by IMISCOE	Academics and most AspirE local teams	Paris, France (hybrid)
18/07/2025	<i>IX Associação Portuguesa de Antropologia (APA) Congress</i> by the APA and the Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo	Academics and Iscte team	Viana do Castelo, Portugal (hybrid)
22/08/2025	<i>19th Deutschsprachiger Japanologentag</i> by Goethe University Frankfurt (GUF)	Academics, and AspirE's local Principal Investigator based at GUF	Frankfurt, Germany
26/08/2025	<i>Symposium on Precarities and Temporalities in Migratory Contexts</i> by the PrecaNord project, the Migration, care and ageing research group and the University of Helsinki	Academics and a representative of the TAU team	Helsinki, Finland
03/09/2025	<i>British Association for Chinese Studies Annual Conference</i> by the University of Leicester	Academics and two representatives of the Iscte team	Leicester, UK
10/09/2025	<i>5th Conference on Asian Studies</i> by the German Association of Asian Studies and the University of Bonn	Representative of the GUF team	Bonn, Germany
23/10/2025	<i>Social Policy Conference</i> by the Social and public policy science and the University of Helsinki	Academics and a representative of the TAU team	Helsinki, Finland
30/10/2025	<i>Panel discussion after the screening of "Blood Berries"</i> by the TAU team	Thai embassies consulate, academics, and students	Helsinki, Finland

15/11/2025	<i>Sophie Research Week</i> by Sophia University	AspirE's local Principal Investigator based at GUF	Tokyo, Japan
17/11/2025	<i>Migration Conversations with Jay Mar Albaos</i> by the SMC team	Government representatives and academics	Quezon City, The Philippines
11 – 12/12/2025	<i>Migration decision-making in Asia-Europe social spaces</i> by the AspirE team	Policy stakeholders, embassy representatives, academics, students	Brussels, Belgium (hybrid)
18/02/2026	<i>The European Turn: A New Chapter in Global Migration from the Philippines</i> by the SMC team	Deputy Head of the Delegation of the EU to the Philippines, private sector representatives, academics, and students	Pasig City, the Philippines

POLICY-ORIENTED EVENTS

Throughout the project, AspirE actively engaged with policymakers, practitioners, and other relevant stakeholders through a series of roundtable discussions at both international and local levels. Rather than limiting dissemination to the end of the project, these events provided opportunities for discussion, feedback, and contextual interpretation of findings as they emerged, fostering dialogue that informed both research and policy development.

A flagship example was the [Policy Lab on EU–Asia Migration](#), held in September 2024 and co-organised by the Centre for European Policy Studies (CEPS) and ULB in Brussels. This lab brought together project partners, policymakers, and stakeholders to discuss the implications of AspirE's Policy Briefs and emerging research insights for EU and Asia migration governance. It provided a structured forum to translate empirical findings into actionable policy recommendations and to explore synergies between research outputs and ongoing policy debates. In addition, AspirE partners organised and participated in numerous local-level policy-oriented events across 11 countries in Asia and Europe, using formats tailored to each context, including roundtables, seminars, panels, workshops, targeted meetings, and webinars. These events gathered between 6 and 85 participants and were conducted in local languages or bilingual formats. Depending on objectives and sensitivities, some events were open to the public, while others were closed-door meetings to facilitate focused discussions. Participants included representatives from government agencies and ministries, embassies and consulates, EU missions, local policymakers, international organisations, and NGOs. The impact of these events is illustrated by selected examples. In Italy, following a press conference at the Italian Senate, the government introduced changes to labour migration policy in late 2024 and 2025, aimed at reducing abuses and exploitative practices affecting migrant workers. In the Finnish–Thai context, sustained attention to the prevention of human trafficking fostered detailed discussions and follow-up exchanges with embassy staff, policymakers, and other stakeholders, contributing to legislative changes that brought foreign berry pickers under seasonal work regulations from 17 February 2025. An overview of those events from the start of the project until the end is presented below. Readers are invited to consult the [advocacy report](#) for more details about those events.

Date	Event & organiser(s)	Participant(s)	Location
30/05/2024	<i>I veri numeri del decreto flussi: un sistema che continua a creare irregolarità</i> (The Real Numbers Behind the Decreto Flussi: A System that Continues to Produce Irregularity) by Ero Straniero and the University of Milan (UMIL)	Representatives from NGOs, academics (n=27)	Rome, Italy
08/07/2024	<i>IOM Consultation Workshop on Vietnam Migration Profile 2023</i> by the International Organisation of Migration and the Consular Department	Government representatives, NGOs and academics (n=70)	Hanoi, Vietnam
13/09/2024	<i>Roundtable discussion and luncheon</i> by the Royal Thai Embassy, Helsinki	Representatives from the Thai and Finnish authorities, media representatives, TAU team (n=35)	Helsinki, Finland
10/10/2024	<i>Vietnamská migrace a perspektivy české migrační politiky</i> (Vietnamese migration and perspectives of Czech migration policy) by the Masaryk University team (MU)	Representatives from the National Equality Body at the Office of the Public Defender of Rights, MU team (n=7)	Brno, the Czech Republic
06/03/2025	<i>Securing migration or enabling vulnerability? Case study on Czech-Vietnamese migration</i> by the MU team	Representatives from the National Equality Body at the Office of the Public Defender of Rights, MU team (n=11)	Brno, the Czech Republic
07/04/2025	<i>Politiche migratorie e mercato del lavoro: un puzzle di difficile soluzione</i> (Migration Policies and the Labor Market: A Difficult Puzzle to Solve) by the Forum Italiano ed Europeo di Ricerche sull'Immigrazione and the University of Turin	Government representatives, NGOs, academics, AspirE's local Principal Investigator based at UMIL (n=40)	Turin, Italy
28/05/2025	<i>Revisiting and Prospecting Philippines-to-Europe Migration: New Trends and Policy Implications</i> by the SMC team	Representatives from government agencies, recruitment agencies, embassies, NGO, academics, and students, SMC team (n=49)	Quezon City, the Philippines
23/08/2025	<i>Revisiting Isan Migration: Lives, Labours, and Mobility Pathways</i> by Mahidol University (MAU), the Research Institute for Languages	Government and media representatives, academics, and	Bangkok, Thailand

	and Cultures of Asia, and the MAU team	students, MAU team (n=50)	
11/09/2025	<i>Enhancing the integration of scientific research into migration policy formulation</i> by the Institute of Sociology and Psychology - Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences (IS-VASS) and the Vietnam Asia Pacific Economic Center (VAPEC)	Policymakers, representatives from governments, departments, ministries, NGOs, and scholars from universities and research institutes, IS-VASS and VAPEC teams (n=85)	Hanoi, Vietnam
23/09/2025	<i>Warum bleiben, warum gehen? Einblicke in politische Einflussfaktoren, Entscheidungsprozesse und Verhalten japanischer Migrant*innen in Deutschland</i> (Why stay, why leave? Insights into political influencing factors, decision-making processes and behaviour of Japanese migrants in Germany) by the GUF team	Academics, economists from the private sector and government side, NGOs representatives, lawyers, local ministries representatives, and Japanese migrants, GUF team (n=25)	Online
06/10/2025	<i>Meeting with the EU office</i> by the EUHK team	Representatives from the EU office in Hong Kong, EUHK team (n=6)	Hong Kong
16/10/2025	<i>Empirical insights and policy implications of the AspirE's Belgium-focused case study</i> by the ULB team	Representatives from embassies and mission to the EU, NGOs, ULB team (n=9)	Brussels, Belgium
24/10/2025	<i>Asian Lives in Europe: a Visual Journey</i> by the Iscte team	Academics and an audience from different backgrounds, Iscte team (n=50)	Lisbon, Portugal
07/11/2025	<i>Contemporary Japanese migration into Europe: a panel discussion</i> by the Institute of Asian Migrations and the Waseda University (WU) team	Academics, students, NGOs and government officials, WU and GUF teams (n=60)	Tokyo, Japan (hybrid)
13/11/2025	<i>Aktuální otázky uprchlického a cizineckého práva</i> (Current Issues in Refugee and Immigration Law) by the Office of the Public Defender of Rights	Judges, government officials, ombudsman specialists, academics, NGO lawyers, international experts, and MU team (n=80)	Brno, the Czech Republic

ONLINE AND ONSITE EXHIBITIONS

AspirE placed a strong emphasis on exhibitions as a fundamental tool for translating research findings into immersive and accessible experiences. Recognising the importance of this approach, a dedicated [web section](#) was created in 2025 to showcase both online and onsite exhibition initiatives, reflecting the project’s commitment to making migration stories widely accessible.

The online exhibition, hosted by ISCTE, “*Asian Lives in Europe: a Visual Journey*”, brings together visual and narrative materials from across the project, including video diaries and symbolic objects representing participants’ experiences. Designed as a permanent digital space, it ensures global accessibility and preserves the project’s findings as a lasting legacy. Inaugurated on 24 October 2025 in the premises of ISCTE, the onsite exhibition includes testimonies from Asian migrants in Portugal, panels on symbolic objects (“Catalogue of Avatars”), and the premiere of the documentary “Songs of Leaving”, extending AspirE’s engagement with public and academic audiences through film. The exhibition will be moved to the Macau Scientific and Cultural Centre for a period of one month. AspirE also organised other onsite exhibitions across Asia and Europe. In Bangkok, the exhibition “*STUCK IN TRANSIT: Isan Lives in Motion*” was held at the Bangkok Art and Culture Centre from 19–31 August 2025, presenting personal objects, photographs, songs, and video diaries alongside a seminar and roundtable discussions. In Khon Kaen, a screening of the documentary “*Blood Berries | หมากไม้*” took place on 20 September 2025 at Khon Kaen University, attended by over 300 participants and accompanied by a panel discussion with former migrant workers, scholars, and film producers. In Brussels, a special version of the mentioned exhibition was hosted at the ULB-VUB Usquare site from December 2025 until January 2026. The exhibition provided a curated selection of materials drawn from both the Lisbon and Thai exhibitions, offering a condensed yet immersive experience of AspirE’s research insights and the lived experiences of aspiring (re)migrants.

DOCUMENTARY FILMS

As part of its commitment to accessible research dissemination, AspirE produced a series of documentary films that translate academic findings into visual narratives. These productions amplify migrants’ voices and experiences, fostering dialogue with audiences beyond academia while reinforcing the project’s engagement with artistic practice, public debate, and human rights advocacy.

A 37-minute documentary [Songs of Leaving](#), produced by the Iscte team, centres on aspiring migrants’ self-recorded audiovisual testimonies (video diaries) and the use of avatars. Drawing on materials collected by all AspirE local research teams, the film puts participants’ own narratives in the spotlight while adhering to the project’s strong ethical framework. In line with its commitment to responsible storytelling and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance, avatars and voice doubling were deliberately employed to safeguard anonymity without compromising emotional depth or narrative agency. Through layered storytelling and visual intimacy, *Songs of Leaving* amplifies migrants’ voices. The film will be disseminated through film festivals, cultural venues, and educational platforms.

Between 2023 and 2025, three documentary films in Thai (with English subtitles) were produced by The Isaan Record team, focusing on the migration of Thai berry pickers to Finland. The Isaan Record uses YouTube (13,6k subscribers) and both their [English Facebook page](#) (32K followers) and their [Thai Facebook page](#) (232K followers) to disseminate news about their documentary films.

- *Bloody Berry* (2023) examines the promises and pitfalls of seasonal berry picking, highlighting how workers, particularly from Thailand’s Isaan region, often return home burdened by debt after migration trajectories that failed to deliver the anticipated

financial security. A sample of the 23-minute documentary film is available on YouTube (186 views for the [Thai version](#), 448 views for the [Thai version with English subtitles](#)). The entire documentary film is accessible on Facebook (920 views for the [Thai version](#)) while a sample was also shared on Facebook (6,4k views for the [Thai version](#), 1,6k view for the [English version](#)). This documentary film won [two awards](#) from the Issara Amantakul Foundation, which promotes freedom of the mass media in Thailand, as well as an award from Amnesty International Thailand.

- *The Berries Blues* (2024) is a 15-minute documentary film further exploring these labour migration dynamics and was screened in Finland, fostering dialogue with European audiences on the structural conditions underpinning seasonal work. A sample of the film was published on YouTube (331 views for the [Thai version](#), 537 views for their [English version](#)). This production was further disseminated through Facebook (64k views for the [Thai version](#), 5,2k views for the [English version](#)).
- *Blood Berries* (2025) provides an in-depth account of the realities behind the so-called “gold rush” of Thai berry picking, grounded in sustained, on-the-ground engagement. This time, the documentary film was subtitled in both Thai and English. The trailer was shared on [YouTube](#) (1k views) and advertised via [Facebook](#) (37k views). [Screened across Thailand and in several European countries](#) (Belgium, Finland, Germany, and Greece), the film centres migrants’ voices and perspectives, emphasising self-representation, long-term engagement, and ethical documentary practice. An additional audiovisual production was shared on their [Thai Facebook page](#) (3k views) to highlight the impact of this documentary film. It recently received the [Best Human Rights Award](#) at the Montreal Women Film Festival. This 52-minute documentary film will be broadcast on Thai PBS for one year.

OTHER DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

On top of academic publications, in-house productions, public presentations, exhibitions, and documentary films, AspirE pursued additional dissemination and exploitation efforts aimed at broadening the visibility and use of the project’s results.

This was achieved through collaboration with media actors beyond the Consortium. Project findings and perspectives were featured in radio programmes (i.e., the [Hong Kong programme](#) “Clear Day Breakfast”, the [Swedish radio broadcaster](#) “Sverige Radio”) and newspaper articles (i.e., the Hong Kong newspaper “Ming Pao” to [present the AspirE project](#) and share the [case of mainland China/Hong Kong, interview on Thai berry pickers](#) in the Finnish magazine “Iso Numero”, a [feature on human trafficking](#) of Thai berry pickers in the Finnish magazine “Suomen Kuvalehti”, [outcomes from the latest event organised by the SMC team](#) on the Dubai newspaper Gulf News). Most of these collaborations were produced in the local language, reaching out to non-academic local audiences. Coverage through institutional communication channels (see Annexe 1), including news features published in French by the [Université libre de Bruxelles](#), [Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon](#), [Waseda University](#), just to name a few. These initiatives further amplified visibility at both national and international levels.

AspirE also engaged in strategic collaboration with other European research initiatives. Joint activities, such as the organisation of a Migrants’ Day [three-part interview series](#) with sister EU-funded projects PACES and DYNAMIG, created opportunities for coordinated outreach. In addition, AspirE contributed a [written piece](#) to the Co-Lab established by the EU-funded project INNOVATE, fostering interdisciplinary dialogue and enhancing the project’s integration within broader European research networks.

2. COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Sharing AspirE’s findings and outputs in meaningful and accessible ways requires a multifaceted communication strategy. This section explores the tools implemented throughout the project and considers how they enhance visibility and engagement.

2.1. AspirE’s website

AspirE disseminates its activities and research findings primarily through its official website, launched in May 2023 (<https://aspire.ulb.be>). The website serves as the project’s central information hub, providing comprehensive and regularly updated content on its objectives and methodology, work packages, team members, and advisory board, as well as its communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

As outlined in the CD&E plan, AspirE’s website is hosted on the ULB institutional web platform, ensuring long-term durability and protection against piracy. The website was developed by the agency "Typi Design" in collaboration with AspirE’s Project Manager and the project’s Principal Investigator. The designs featured on the website were created using Canva, for which AspirE holds a three-year subscription. The site includes the following sections: Home, Research, Team, News, Impact, Exhibitions, and Contact (see Figure 3). The Exhibitions section is the latest addition to the home page. On the top right, social media pages and email are directly accessible.

Figure 2. Upper menu bar of the project’s website

In relation to website analytics and cookie management, the project uses Matomo to collect statistical data on website traffic and user interaction. Matomo is an open-source analytics platform that prioritises data protection and user privacy. The data collected are anonymised, not shared with third parties, and securely hosted on ULB servers. For cookie consent management, the website uses CookieYes, which ensures compliance with applicable data protection and ePrivacy regulations by allowing users to manage and customise their cookie preferences.

Figure 3. Visitor map worldwide (19/12/2023)

Figure 4. Visitor map worldwide (19/12/2024)

Figure 5. Visitor map worldwide (27/08/2026)

The AspirE website has attracted an increasingly international audience over the course of the project. While the majority of visitors originate from Europe (Belgium, France, and Germany), significant traffic also comes from Asia (Hong Kong, Japan, and the Philippines) as well as the United States. As illustrated in Figures 3, 4, and 5, the number of visits has steadily increased since the website’s launch in May 2023. Visits rose from 2 619 (May 2023 - December 2024) to 8 847 over the same reference period and reached a total of 12,609 by February 2026. The geographical distribution of visitors also broadened significantly between Figures 3 and 4, before stabilising towards the end of the project. Overall, the data indicate sustained growth in visibility.

Website traffic reflects the project’s online visibility, and this can be achieved via different channel types (see Figure 6). Most users discover the site through search engines, demonstrating that its content is well indexed and easily findable via search engines such as Google. Social media platforms (particularly Facebook, Twitter/X, and LinkedIn) represent another important entry point, especially when publications, events, or project updates are actively shared. A further share of visitors arrive via institutional and partner channels, such as newsletters and external websites that reference or feature the project.

Figure 6. Channel types through which the project’s website was found (19/12/2024)

CHANNEL TYPE	▼ VISITS	ACTIONS	ACTIONS PER VISIT	AVG. TIME ON WEBSITE	BOUNCE RATE
Direct Entry	57.2% 7,211	24,726	3.4	3 min 39s	45%
+ Search Engines	24.8% 3,122	8,416	2.7	2 min 3s	57%
+ Social Networks	12.6% 1,592	4,395	2.8	2 min 16s	50%
+ Websites	5.2% 662	2,412	3.6	3 min 37s	47%
+ Campaigns	0.2% 19	70	3.7	7 min 11s	37%

2.2. Podcasts

The [AspirE podcast series](#) translates research findings and field experiences into accessible, episodes, tackling key themes emerging from the project. To date, three podcast series have been published on the project website and on platforms such as [SoundCloud](#) and Spotify, and have also been featured on [ULB’s podcast webpage](#).

The first series (October–December 2023), comprising seven episodes, introduced the project and presented its selected migration corridors between Europe and Asia. It has accumulated 91 plays on SoundCloud and 50 plays on Spotify. The second series (October 2024) focused on the findings of Work Package 2, particularly policy content analysis and interviews with migration experts, and concluded with policy recommendations for more humane and inclusive migration governance in the EU. Due to financial constraints, it was published only on Spotify, where it has recorded 30 listens. The third series (December 2025) presents the results of Work Package 3, highlighting interviews with aspiring (re)migrants and the project’s social network mapping component. As it was released recently, it is too early to assess its reach. A fourth and final series is currently in preparation and will soon be released. It will focus on the results of Work Package 4, including insights from video diaries and focus-group discussions.

Although listening figures remain modest, this reflects common structural challenges associated with specialised research podcasts. Nonetheless, the series constitutes an important dissemination tool, complementing written outputs and supporting the project’s objective of communicating research findings in an accessible and human-centred format.

2.3. Social media presence

The AspirE project maintained active social media channels to support the timely dissemination of outputs and events. To ensure regular and coordinated communication, a structured internal process was established: consortium partners submitted updates (e.g., events, publications) via Google Forms, which allowed the project team to plan and maintain a publication calendar.

Initially, AspirE was active on X/Twitter and Facebook. The publication calendar established the strategic use of visual materials, consistent posting frequency (targeting at least three posts per week), and hashtags relevant to migration and research to increase visibility and participation in broader conversations. Following changes in platform moderation policies and limitations in analytics, the project discontinued its X/Twitter account on 3 February 2025. In its place, AspirE created a LinkedIn account, which now has 174 followers. Facebook remains the most popular platform, with 428 followers. These channels have enabled the project to reach a diverse audience and quantitatively monitor engagement, ensuring that key outputs and events receive consistent visibility.

FACEBOOK

AspirE’s Facebook account, launched in June 2023, has been the project’s most successful social media platform. Following the tailored publication calendar, between two and three posts were shared weekly. The account has steadily grown, increasing from 283 followers in December 2024 to 428 followers at present, reflecting sustained engagement and visibility.

Figure 7. Number of likes and followers on Facebook (27/02/2026)

Facebook’s Meta Business Suite provides detailed analytics on the reach and engagement of content shared on the platform. As shown in Figure 8, covering January 2025 to February 2026, AspirE’s posts were viewed approximately 46k times and generated 1,5k interactions. The most popular content included webinars, trainings, workshops, and exhibitions. These figures capture both users who visited the page directly and those who encountered the content through other channels (e.g., shares by other pages, platforms, or websites), extending the project’s visibility beyond its immediate followers and offering insight into how widely AspirE’s communication circulates across networks.

Figure 8. Overall presentation of Facebook statistics (19/12/2024)

LINKEDIN

AspirE launched its LinkedIn account in February 2025 and has since gained 174 followers. As a platform with a professional audience, posts are written in a slightly different style but follow the same publication calendar as Facebook. Due to its network-oriented nature, LinkedIn has become a useful channel to share the project’s work and developments with stakeholders and key actors in the field of migration.

Figure 9. Number of followers on LinkedIn (27/02/2026)

Since its launch, the AspirE LinkedIn account has generated close to 13k impressions, demonstrating decent visibility within a professional audience. On LinkedIn, impressions refer to the number of times posts are displayed on users’ feeds. Engagement with the content is reflected in 355 reactions, 3 comments, and 15 reposts. Reactions (likes and other response buttons) extend the content beyond the project’s immediate network to new professional circles. The evolution of impressions over time (Figure 10) shows three notable peaks in April 2025, October 2025, and January 2026. Chronologically, these peaks align with Webinar 3, the exhibition in Lisbon, and the final conference wrap-up alongside the release of the last batch of policy briefs. Interestingly, this pattern is broadly comparable to the Facebook analytics, particularly the pronounced peak in April 2025, suggesting that key project milestones generated heightened visibility across platforms. The organic impressions trend (views generated without paid promotion) further confirms that the project’s visibility is primarily driven by content relevance and network engagement rather than sponsored dissemination.

Figure 9. Evolution of impressions (23/02/2026)

Facebook has been AspirE’s strongest social media channel in terms of overall reach and engagement, with considerable growth in followers and high visibility. LinkedIn, in turn, has proven particularly effective for reaching a specialised and professional audience. Together, the two platforms serve complementary purposes, strengthening broad outreach and strategic engagement.

2.4. Newsletter

Since September 2023, AspirE has been publishing a bimonthly newsletter using Brevo, with all issues available on the [project website](#). To date, 14 newsletters have been sent to an expanding subscriber base, which has grown from 81 in December 2024 to 106 subscribers in February 2026. The final newsletter is scheduled for shortly after the end of the project, following the last consortium meeting in early March 2026.

According to Brevo's statistics, the newsletters have achieved a 66% open rate and a 14% click rate, reflecting active interest among recipients. These figures are approximate, as some subscribers may use email privacy features that prevent tracking.

2.5. Partner communication channels and others

To further disseminate AspirE's findings and activities, team members are encouraged to use their respective institutional communication channels. Some partners have featured the project on their institutional websites, while others share AspirE-related content through their active social media accounts, particularly Facebook.

Each partner is responsible for ensuring that their institution highlights AspirE's results, with a focus on local-level outcomes and content in the local language to effectively reach relevant stakeholders and audiences. As project coordinator, ULB monitors and maintains an overview of AspirE's presence across partners' communication channels, including external channels beyond the consortium (see Annex 1).

3. CONCLUSION

The AspirE project's dissemination strategies, as outlined in its CD&E Plan and analysed throughout this report, demonstrate a strong commitment to engaging both academic and non-academic audiences through multiple channels. By combining social media activity (on Facebook and LinkedIn, following the discontinuation of X/Twitter), participation in events with international institutions, webinars, workshops, and targeted collaborations, AspirE has worked to increase visibility, foster interactions, and share key research findings with a global audience.

While challenges in audience engagement remain, the project's strategies, supported by structured content planning, regular posting, and targeted promotion, have laid a solid foundation for outreach and provided valuable insights into content reach and interaction. These efforts ensured that AspirE's research reached key stakeholders and contributed to broader discussions on migration policy, methodology, and human-centred approaches.

By keeping both academic and non-academic audiences informed, AspirE has reinforced its commitment to human-centred migration research and encouraged public engagement in migration-related debates. Although the project has concluded, the website and social media accounts will remain active, serving as platforms to share future publications and outputs from ongoing collaborations. This final report provides a comprehensive overview of the impact of AspirE's dissemination activities, documenting the project's online presence, outreach, and overall influence.

ANNEX 1 – Communication channels featuring the AspirE project

Partners	Website	Social Media	Other
Université libre de Bruxelles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AspirE main website https://aspire.ulb.be • Maison des Sciences Humaines – EAST https://msh.ulb.ac.be/ • ULB podcast webpage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AspirE Facebook (@AspirE2023EUproject) • EAST Facebook • AspirE X / Twitter (@AspirE_EU_Asia) • EAST X / Twitter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AspirE Newsletter • EAST Newsletter
Tampere University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tampere University's website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finland-focused Facebook page • Institutional X / Twitter account 	
Masaryk University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Masaryk University's website 		
University Institute of Lisbon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iscte website • Centre of Research and Sociology studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional X / Twitter account 	
Goethe University Frankfurt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GUF website 		
Scalabrini Migration Center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMC website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional Facebook page • LinkedIn 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linktr
Mahidol University		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia (RILCA) Facebook page 	
The Isaan Record	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Isaan Record website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facebook page (in English and Thai) • X / Twitter account 	
Waseda University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institute of Asian Migrations website 		
IS-VASS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IS-VASS website 		
UMIL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UMIL website 		

EU projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DYNAMIG website • PACES website • INNOVATE website 		
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre for European Policy Studies website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEPS X / Twitter account 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEPS Newsletter